

Deliverable 3.1

TECHNICAL ARCHITECTURE AND PROTOCOL FOR ANONYMISATION AND SYNTHETISATION

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Executive Summary

Deliverable 3.1 presents the technical architecture and protocol for anonymisation and synthetisation within the PHEMS federated healthcare ecosystem. This document outlines the design, functional requirements, deployment strategies, and integration of privacy-enhancing technologies (PETs) aimed at safeguarding sensitive healthcare data while supporting advanced research and innovation.

The PHEMS architecture integrates VEIL.AI's anonymisation and synthetisation services to transform sensitive patient data into anonymised or synthetic datasets. These services enable secure data sharing and analysis across pediatric healthcare institutions in compliance with data protection regulations such as GDPR. The technical design incorporates robust security measures, including encryption, access control, and secure deployment environments, to mitigate privacy risks.

Key components include the processing layer for data transformation, federated analytics for secure data collaboration, and integration with hospital data environments. Use cases such as pediatric cardiac benchmarking, sepsis detection, and hemophilia treatment optimisation demonstrate practical applications of these technologies. Future enhancements focus on expanding privacy measures, integrating emerging data types, and fostering continuous improvement through stakeholder engagement.

This deliverable ensures that PHEMS can leverage healthcare data for impactful research while maintaining the highest standards of data privacy and security.

1. List of Abbreviations and Definitions

ABBREVIATION	DESCRIPTION
PHEMS	Paediatric Hospitals as European drivers for multi-party computation and synthetic data generation capabilities across clinical specialities and data types
PII	Personally Identifiable Information
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation - A regulation in EU law on data protection and privacy in the European Union and the European Economic Area.
EHDS	European Health Data Space - An emerging initiative by the European Union to promote better exchange and access to different types of health data to support healthcare delivery, research, and policymaking.
CCPA	California Consumer Privacy Act
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprises - Businesses whose personnel numbers fall below certain limits.
PET	Privacy Enhancing Technology
TEE	Trusted Executing Environment
OMOP CDM	Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership Common Data Model - A standardized data model that facilitates the harmonization of disparate observational databases for comparative effectiveness research
GAN	Generative Adversarial Network
API	Application Programming Interface
AI/ML	Artificial Intelligence / Machine Learning
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable - A set of principles to guide data management and stewardship practices, making data more usable and enhancing data sharing.
IAM	Identity and Access Management
TLS/SSL	Cryptographic protocols that provide secure communication over a network by encrypting data, authenticating parties, and ensuring data integrity.
VM	Virtual Machine
CI/CD	Continuous Integration/Continuous Delivery or Continuous Deployment. It's a software development practice where developers integrate code changes frequently and automatically, and the software is delivered rapidly and reliably through automation.
ACL	Access Control List
PICU	Paediatric Intensive Care Unit
Anonymisation and Synthetisation	The document uses the terms in the following ways depending on the context <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Anonymisation and Synthetisation service: the technical component capable of producing anonymised and synthetic data on-demand.

	<ol style="list-style-type: none">2. Anonymisation and Synthetisation techniques: the different methods to transform the sensitive data into non-sensitive / non-personal / anonymous.3. Anonymisation and Synthetisation: when describing in general the process of transforming sensitive data. <p>In diagrams in this document the above terms also have the following short expressions</p> <p>Anonymous data: meaning both anonymised and synthetic data</p> <p>Anonymisation Service: same as Anonymisation and Synthetisation service</p>
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2. Introduction

This document provides an overview and technical protocol for data anonymisation and synthetisation within the PHEMS federated healthcare ecosystem.

Data anonymisation and synthetisation are privacy-enhancing technologies (PETs) that transform healthcare systems' data into a more secure, privacy-preserving representation. These processes enable researchers and healthcare professionals to utilise data for analysis while minimising risks to patient privacy, thereby supporting data-driven insights without compromising sensitive information.

2.1. Purpose of the document

The purpose of this document is to provide a comprehensive overview of data anonymisation and synthetisation components, their technical architecture, key algorithms, deployment strategies, and integration considerations within the PHEMS federated healthcare ecosystem. It aims to define the functional and security requirements and outline the practical deployment of these components.

2.2. Scope of the document

The scope of this document includes the design and implementation of anonymisation and synthetisation technologies within the PHEMS project. It covers the technical architecture of these components, their integration into existing hospital data infrastructure, and their role within the larger federation architecture. Additionally, it addresses the specific benefits, challenges, use cases, and future directions for anonymisation and data synthetisation.

This document does not delve into the detailed implementation of individual software components but emphasises the architectural view.

2.3. Document structure

This document is organised into multiple key sections. It starts with an overview of the anonymisation and synthetisation concepts, followed by the technical architecture, functional requirements, component design, deployment plan, integration strategies, use cases, and future considerations. Each section is intended to build upon the previous one to provide a cohesive understanding of the architecture and implementation.

2.4. Intended audience

The intended audience for this document includes technical teams working on data privacy, data architects, software developers, privacy officers, and healthcare data scientists involved in PHEMS projects. It targets stakeholders responsible for regulatory compliance and data privacy in the healthcare ecosystem. It is also suitable for individuals seeking to

understand the integration of anonymisation and synthetisation within healthcare data management.

2.5. Reference documents

This document draws on insights from

1. D2.1 Federation architecture

and other foundational documents related to data governance, privacy, and federated healthcare systems. Specific references to these documents will be provided throughout the text to support the architectural and implementation decisions.

2.6. Anonymisation overview

This section will introduce anonymisation, discussing its principles and importance within the PHEMS ecosystem.

2.6.1. Introduction

Anonymisation is the process of transforming personal data containing personally identifiable information (PII) to prevent the identification of individuals, either directly or indirectly. In healthcare datasets, anonymisation plays a crucial role in safeguarding patient privacy, enabling data sharing for research while complying with privacy regulations. Anonymisation techniques can include suppression, generalisation, and perturbation, each with varying impacts on data quality and utility. By applying anonymisation techniques, sensitive patient information can be effectively protected, thus reducing privacy risks while maintaining data utility for valuable insights and decision-making.

2.6.2. Benefits

The benefits of anonymisation are substantial, particularly in the context of healthcare data. Anonymisation enables data sharing across organisations while complying with privacy regulations such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) in Europe, the California Consumer Privacy Act (CCPA) in California, United States, the upcoming European Health Data Space (EHDS), and the EU AI Act, both in Europe. By transforming sensitive data, healthcare providers can collaborate on data-driven research and innovation without exposing patients to risks associated with data misuse. Anonymised data retains analytical value, making it a powerful tool for research, quality improvement, and healthcare studies in a privacy-compliant manner. Additionally, anonymised data facilitates the development of advanced data-driven solutions, such as predictive analytics and AI models, which can help improve patient outcomes and foster medical breakthroughs. Ultimately, anonymisation provides a way to maximise the value of data while upholding ethical standards and protecting individual privacy.

2.6.3. Challenges

Despite its numerous benefits, anonymisation presents several challenges that must be addressed to ensure effective implementation. One of the primary challenges is the trade-off between privacy and data utility. As data is anonymised, it may lose some of its original details, which can reduce the richness of the data, limiting its research value. Achieving an optimal balance between data utility and privacy protection is a complex task that requires sophisticated techniques and an in-depth understanding of data characteristics. Another challenge lies in mitigating the risk of re-identification. Advances in data analytics and the availability of external datasets increase the possibility that anonymised data could be re-identified, potentially compromising patient privacy. This requires ongoing vigilance, advanced privacy-preserving techniques, and frequent risk assessments to ensure that anonymisation remains effective over time. Additionally, anonymisation requires careful planning to comply with evolving data protection regulations while maintaining data quality.

2.6.4. Prospects

The prospects for anonymisation are promising, particularly as new techniques and technologies emerge to enhance privacy protections. Advances in privacy-enhancing technologies (PETs), such as differential privacy, k-anonymity, and homomorphic encryption, are expected to be increasingly important in enhancing anonymisation efforts. These technologies help maintain the utility of anonymised data while minimising privacy risks, thus allowing organisations to strike an optimal balance between privacy and usability.

Moreover, as data sharing and collaboration become more essential to advancing healthcare, the adoption of sophisticated anonymisation practices is likely to grow. The future will also see a stronger focus on integrating anonymisation with other privacy measures, such as synthetic data generation and federated learning, to create comprehensive privacy-preserving data ecosystems and robust protections that support both research and regulatory compliance.

2.6.5. Conclusion

In summary, anonymisation is critical for enabling data-driven healthcare innovation while protecting patient privacy. Its ability to transform personal data into a form that allows for secure analysis and sharing makes it indispensable for advancing medical research and improving patient care. Although challenges such as balancing data utility and privacy and mitigating re-identification risks must be addressed, the ongoing development of privacy-enhancing technologies offers a promising path forward. By continuing to advance anonymisation techniques and integrate them with other privacy-preserving measures, the healthcare industry can fully leverage the potential of data to drive innovation while ensuring patient privacy and regulatory compliance.

2.7. Synthetisation overview

Synthetisation involves generating artificial datasets that accurately reflect the statistical properties of real data without containing any identifiable information about real individuals. The benefits of synthetisation are significant, particularly in healthcare research and development. Data synthetisation is used as a privacy-preserving technique that allows organisations to share and analyse patient data while reducing the risks associated with handling sensitive information and ensuring compliance with privacy regulations such as GDPR.

Synthetic data can also serve as an alternative when access to real data is restricted, supporting research and model development without compromising patient privacy. Healthcare providers and researchers can use synthetic datasets to perform extensive training, testing, and validation of machine learning models while minimising privacy risks. Additionally, synthetic data can be generated to address data scarcity, especially in rare disease research, where obtaining large volumes of real patient data is challenging.

Synthetisation techniques include generative models such as GANs (Generative Adversarial Networks) and variational autoencoders, which can produce high-quality synthetic data. Synthetic data complements anonymisation, providing additional tools to enable safe and effective data analysis, particularly when sharing data across borders.

Synthetisation, despite its advantages, comes with challenges that must be considered for effective implementation. One of the key challenges is ensuring that synthetic data retains the statistical utility of the original dataset while eliminating any risk of re-identification and avoiding potential privacy risks such as model memorisation. Creating high-quality synthetic data that maintains the relationships and distributions found in the real data requires sophisticated modelling techniques and careful validation. Additionally, synthetic data may inadvertently introduce biases or fail to capture subtle but important patterns in real data. Addressing these issues requires the ongoing development of robust generation algorithms and a thorough assessment of data utility and quality.

Although challenges such as maintaining data utility and addressing biases must be tackled, the future of synthetisation in healthcare is promising. Advances in generative modelling techniques enhance synthetic data quality, making it more reliable and valuable for research and analysis. As data privacy regulations continue to evolve, the adoption of synthetic data is expected to increase, providing a powerful tool for privacy-preserving data sharing.

With continued development, synthetisation will play an increasingly critical role in advancing healthcare research, improving patient outcomes, and enabling privacy-preserving data-driven healthcare advancements.

2.8. Anonymity: Anonymisation vs. Synthetisation

Anonymisation and synthetisation are powerful tools for privacy preservation, but they have different strengths, limitations, and use cases. Anonymisation modifies existing datasets to

remove personally identifiable information, while synthetisation generates new, artificial datasets that resemble the original data statistically.

Anonymisation, although irreversible, is often suitable when maintaining a direct link to the original data is necessary, such as for certain types of compliance and auditing. Synthetisation, on the other hand, is useful for creating entirely non-identifiable datasets for model training, testing, and validation or when the risk of re-identification must be minimised.

Choosing between anonymisation and synthetisation depends on data privacy, utility, and compliance requirements.

3. Design Document

3.1. System Architecture Overview

3.1.1. Overview of the ecosystem architecture

PHEMS Technical Architecture (ref: D2.1) is a comprehensive and structured approach to manage and execute research projects within a federated data environment with capability to anonymise or generate synthetic data for research purposes. At the core of this architecture is the goal to enable easy researcher access to multiple data controllers through dedicated workspaces and protecting privacy of the individuals in the data. Communication between workspaces and data controllers is achieved by leveraging Shared Services that facilitate streamlined and cohesive federated operations within the network, alongside direct interfacing via APIs.

3.1.2. Key Components of the PHEMS architecture

The PHEMS system architecture is designed to securely and efficiently utilise health data in paediatrics. It integrates various components to ensure harmonisation, privacy, and accessibility of data.

- Data sources from participating hospitals, including electronic health records, lab results, patient monitor data, and medical imaging. This data is securely stored and standardised using the Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership (OMOP) common data model (CDM) for interoperability.
- Data anonymisation and synthetisation service, which uses advanced algorithms to convert sensitive health data into anonymous data, ensuring privacy while maintaining utility for research.
- Federated analytics network enabling distributed data analysis without centralising sensitive data or transferring it across borders. This allows secure collaboration among data controllers while keeping data under the original controller's control, supporting multi-jurisdictional research.

- User interfaces and APIs provide access to the PHEMS ecosystem, enabling data discovery, request submissions, federated analytics, and access to anonymised and synthetic datasets for researchers, SMEs, innovators, and other stakeholders.

3.1.3. Placement and role of the anonymisation and synthetisation components within the architecture

The VEIL.AI anonymisation and synthetisation service is an essential part of the processing layer, providing a mechanism for safeguarding patient privacy in compliance with data protection regulations. This service performs two primary functions: anonymisation of data to prevent disclosure of patient identity, and synthetisation, the generation of synthetic data that replicates the statistical properties of original data without containing identifiable information.

The anonymisation and synthetisation service will be installed in each hospital environment and integrated with the PHEMS federated solution via a Kubernetes service. This Kubernetes service is configured to act as an intermediary between the PHEMS ecosystem and the anonymisation and synthetisation service. The OMOP data will be accessed directly within each participating hospital's secure environment, without requiring sensitive data to leave the hospital's premises. Access to the anonymisation and synthetisation service should be limited following the least access principle.

The main benefits of this approach are:

Broader Use: Installation in the hospitals' compute environments, outside the federated PHEMS Kubernetes ecosystem, will allow anonymization and synthetic data generation for all hospital-controlled datasets, not just OMOP data via the PHEMS architecture.

Enhanced Security Measures: Sensitive data can be processed within a security-hardened environment close to the data, instead of being sent to a PHEMS federated Kubernetes environment, improving control over the data and reducing exposure risk. If required, secure access to the data can be optimally configured for each hospital's OMOP data source, ensuring no compromise on security.

3.1.4. Anonymisation in the Data Layer

The data layer is designed to ensure the security of patient data and the integrity of results. To minimise risk, a read-only replica of the subset of data held by the data controller is recommended for research purposes to increase scalability and stability by isolating research workloads, protecting master database performance and day-to-day operations. This prevents full data exposure in the event of access control errors and reduces potential performance impact on the master database. Privacy is maintained through anonymisation and synthetisation techniques, as well as encryption for data at rest and in transit.

Key to the data layer is the standardisation of data through the OMOP Common Data Model, ensuring interoperability and readiness for analysis. The data anonymisation and synthetisation service creates anonymised or synthetic OMOP datasets that mimic the

statistical properties of real data, enabling data sharing without compromising sensitive information.

3.1.5. Anonymisation and Data Models

In the PHEMS project, OMOP CDM is used as the primary data model. The OMOP CDM is a widely adopted standard that transforms data from various sources into a common format facilitating the integration of data from different hospitals, allowing consistent analysis of diverse datasets and overcoming data heterogeneity challenges. It supports the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) data principles by making data findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. It includes domains like person, visit, condition, medication, procedure, measurement, and more, each with specific conventions for data representation.

In the PHEMS architecture there is an on-demand algorithmic anonymisation and synthetisation service for OMOP data that produces subject level anonymous data for research purposes comparable to the original OMOP data.

3.1.5.1. Anonymisation in Processing Layer

The processing layer of the PHEMS project is crucial for data handling tasks, including anonymisation, synthetisation, and federated analytics.

3.1.5.1.1. Data Anonymisation and Synthetisation

A core component is the on-demand anonymisation and synthetisation service, designed to protect patient privacy while ensuring data quality and utility for research. Anonymisation removes or modifies identifiable information using techniques like suppression, noise addition, data swapping, and generalisation, tailored to each use case. Synthetisation creates synthetic datasets with similar statistical properties to original data but without identifiable information, using advanced machine learning techniques. These services are robust and scalable to handle large data volumes while maintaining privacy and utility.

3.1.5.1.2. Anonymisation for Federated Analytics and Federated Learning

The processing layer also features a federated analytics network that allows data analysis across multiple sources without centralising data. Data remains with each controller, and only analytics algorithms are shared, ensuring control and privacy. This network supports various analytics tasks and includes dynamic access permissions and real-time exploration. The on-demand anonymisation and synthetisation service can be used before any federated analytics are executed to increase privacy protection. Federated nodes execute jobs, manage anonymised and synthetic data queries, and provide results securely.

The PHEMS federated learning architecture supports collaborative machine learning without sharing sensitive patient data. To even further increase the privacy protection, it is suggested to anonymise or use synthetic data for AI/ML model training in PHEMS architecture.

3.1.6. Data Controller Environment

Each Data Controller in the PHEMS architecture provides a runtime environment according to the implementation specifications. Participating hospitals, serving as data controllers, will host a Kubernetes-based computation environment for executing algorithms.

In PHEMS, this Kubernetes-based environment will orchestrate the federated analytics network and also use the anonymisation and synthetisation service via a Kubernetes intermediary.

3.1.7. Integration of Anonymisation and Synthetisation in PHEMS architecture

In the PHEMS federated analytics network, data remains at its source, and only algorithms are shared, protecting sensitive raw data. The anonymisation and synthetisation service generates anonymised and synthetic datasets from this raw data as part of the PHEMS federated architecture. These anonymous datasets, devoid of identifiable information, are stored in a specialised repository, making them accessible for queries and analytics without compromising privacy. This approach allows researchers to perform a wide range of analytical tasks using anonymised or synthetic data while ensuring data privacy and security.

The architecture employs an Identity and Access Management (IAM) component to manage data processing operations like anonymisation and synthetic data generation requests, ensuring that only authorised users can execute these tasks. Each data controller hosts a federated node, which includes a Job Execution Agent to manage analytics tasks and a Data Agent to handle anonymisation and synthetic data queries and dataset creation. These agents connect securely to project-specific shared services to pull approved workloads, execute them, and store results, ensuring a controlled and synchronised environment.

The system includes a review and release tool for monitoring the data processing lifecycle, managed by an anonymisation data scientist who oversees the generation and release of anonymised and synthetic datasets.

Figure 1. High level system architecture for PHEMS during PoC phase. (reference D2.1)

Figure 2: The processing layer flow diagram for Federated Analytics use cases.

3.2. Functional Requirements

3.2.1. Detailed functional requirements of the anonymisation and synthetisation components

The VEIL.AI anonymisation and synthetisation service will be available on-demand, allowing initiation of anonymisation, synthetisation and to adjust the anonymisation criteria and configurations as necessary. The anonymisation and synthetisation service will be scaled appropriately proportionally to the volume of the input data.

Since input data will be structured according to the OMOP CDM, the service will be configured for both:

Categorical data: For tables without a time dimension, the service will apply anonymisation techniques appropriate for static data.

Time-Series data: For tables with a time dimension, the service will apply anonymisation techniques that preserve temporal relationships.

The VEIL.AI anonymisation and synthetisation service will have specialised endpoints to handle the OMOP CDM data and will use pre-configured anonymisation and synthetisation settings optimised for OMOP CDM data structures. These settings can be changed or overridden, tailoring the process to meet specific requirements. The results of both anonymisation and synthetisation processes will be exported as files, formatted following the OMOP CDM schema. This format compatibility allows the re-ingestion of the processed data into a compatible database environment. The service will read the OMOP CDM input data from the database or from OMOP CDM table-specific files exported from the database.

Data Access

The VEIL.AI anonymisation and synthetisation service will need access to the original dataset that needs to be anonymised or synthesised. As input, the original dataset should be structured as tabular data, with well-defined columns and data types. The quality of the synthetic data depends on the quality and quantity of the original dataset.

Privacy Settings Configuration

Depending on the requirements, privacy parameters must be configured appropriately for the use case. Privacy parameters affect the risk of re-identification of the anonymised or synthetic data set as well as the utility and representativeness of the results.

Usage Context

The choice of an anonymisation method or synthesiser depends on the use case. Some synthesisers, especially, require experience with data engineering, model training, hyperparameter tuning, and managing potential issues such as mode collapse. Users should be comfortable with machine learning workflows.

3.3. Component Design

3.3.1. Detailed design of anonymisation & synthetisation component

The VEIL.AI anonymisation and synthetisation service will implement a combination of anonymisation and synthetisation techniques for categorical and time-series data, including:

Noise Addition: Randomisation of data values to mask identity without significantly distorting data utility.

Data Swapping: Replacement or permutation of data values between records to prevent re-identification.

Generalisation: Conversion of specific values to broader categories or ranges to reduce identifiability while preserving analytical value.

Synthetisation: Generation of synthetic values within the anonymised dataset to replace potentially identifiable elements.

3.4. Security Considerations

3.4.1. Security measures implemented in the design

Encryption mechanisms for data at rest and in transit are implemented by utilising AES-256 for data encryption at rest and using TLS/SSL for secure data transmission. Access controls, such as role-based access control, ensure least privileged access with integration with Microsoft Entra ID (Azure Active Directory) for identity management and multi-factor authentication. Secure key management involves using Azure Key Vault for secure storage of encryption keys, along with rotation and revocation policies for keys. Security features of Azure, such as Azure Security Center, provide continuous security posture monitoring and alerts, with integration into Azure Sentinel for threat detection. Comprehensive audit logging and monitoring is also employed, with logging of access and actions taken, utilising Azure Monitor for centralised monitoring and analysis of logs.

Key elements of the security architecture are:

- Encryption for data at rest and in transit
- Access controls (e.g., role-based access control, Microsoft Entra ID)
- Secure key management (Key Vault)
- Security features of Azure (e.g., Azure Security Center)
- Audit logging and monitoring

3.4.2. Potential vulnerabilities and mitigation strategies

The design of the system takes into account potential vulnerabilities that could affect the security of data and the overall architecture. A thorough analysis of possible attack vectors, such as data inference attacks, is conducted to identify areas where data privacy may be compromised. Additionally, the vulnerabilities specifically associated with synthetic data generation are assessed, as these methods may introduce risks related to data fidelity and potential unintended leakage of original data patterns. To mitigate these risks, data leakage prevention strategies are implemented, including rigorous data masking, access control policies, and monitoring mechanisms. Network security measures are put in place to ensure secure communication within the environment, such as the use of virtual networks and private endpoints to restrict access to critical components. Finally, robust incident response plans and disaster recovery procedures are established to minimise the impact of any security breach and ensure system resilience in the face of potential threats.

4. Deployment Plan

4.1. Deployment Architecture

4.1.1. Overview of the deployment environment

The deployment of the VEIL.AI Anonymisation and Data Synthetisation Engine is designed to run in a secure compute environment. The service is provided as a container or a VM image to be deployed in each hospital secure environment alongside a Kubernetes intermediary deployed in the PHEMS Kubernetes ecosystem. The service must be deployed in a Trusted Executing Environment (TEE) such as AWS Nitro, Azure Confidential Computing, or Azure Confidential Container. The output, including anonymised or synthesised data, is stored in designated cloud or file system storage with encryption at rest.

4.1.2. Infrastructure components

The deployment infrastructure comprises the following essential components:

Trusted Executing Environment (TEE): An execution environment that supports the execution of the VEIL.AI service.

Kubernetes intermediary: PHEMS Kubernetes service acting as an intermediary between the PHEMS federated architecture and VEIL.AI's service.

Data storage: Hospitals' data must be hosted in secure storage, such as cloud-based object storage or on-premises file systems, ensuring encrypted data both at rest and in transit.

Network configuration: Secure networking between the compute environment and the data storage is required to access input and output data to protect sensitive data.

Encryption mechanisms: Data stored in the compute environment, both input and output, must be encrypted at rest to protect sensitive patient data.

Access control: Proper access control mechanisms, such as IAM, must be enforced outside the VEIL.AI service to restrict unauthorised access to both the compute environment and the data storage systems.

4.2. Deployment Workflow

4.2.1. Step-by-step guide to deploying the software components

Provisioning the Trusted Execution Environment: Set up the Trusted Execution Environment that meets the hardware and security requirements for the VEIL.AI service.

Deployment and configuration of the Kubernetes intermediary: Deploy and configure the Kubernetes intermediary to access VEIL.AI's service deployed in the trusted execution environment.

Configuring the data storage: Ensure that the input data from hospitals is accessible from the compute environment by connecting to the cloud or file system storage that contains the input data. The VEIL.AI service must be provided means to access encrypted data.

Deploying the container/VM image: Use the container/VM image provided by VEIL.AI and deploy it within the compute environment.

Data pre-processing (data engineering): Specify data inputs and work with VEIL.AI to pre-process the data to be optimally suitable for data anonymisation. Some of the pre-processing steps may need to be done before the data is given to the VEIL.AI service. Some of the data engineering transformations may be done by the service.

Service configuration: Work with VEIL.AI to optimally configure the service for the specific anonymisation or data synthetisation use cases, taking into account data value types, ranges, dependencies, distributions, and other properties.

Executing the service: Run the VEIL.AI service to process the input data, generating anonymised or synthesised output data in the designated storage location.

Post-processing and validation: Verify the quality of the anonymised or synthesised data, and ensure that the data meets the expected utility and anonymisation criteria.

Reporting and output delivery: Review the reports generated by the service and deliver the final anonymised or synthesised data.

4.2.2. CI/CD pipeline description

The VEIL.AI service is delivered through a robust and high-quality continuous integration/continuous deployment (CI/CD) pipeline. The pipeline automates the building, testing, and deployment of the VEIL.AI container or VM image and the Kubernetes intermediary, ensuring that each release meets stringent quality standards. Key stages in the CI/CD pipeline include:

1. **Code integration:** Developers commit changes to the VEIL.AI codebase, which is automatically integrated into a shared repository.
2. **Automated testing:** Upon integration, the code undergoes a suite of automated tests, including unit, integration, and security tests, to ensure that no vulnerabilities or bugs are introduced.
3. **Containerisation or image building:** Once the code passes testing, it is packaged as a container image or VM image that includes all necessary dependencies and configurations required for the service to run in the target environment.
4. **Deployment to test:** The container or VM image is deployed to a staging environment, where further testing is conducted.
5. **Production deployment:** After successful validation in test, the container or VM image is promoted to production, where it is made available to be deployed by the PHEMS project.
6. **Rollback:** If necessary, the pipeline can automatically trigger a rollback to a previous stable version to minimise downtime and ensure service continuity.

5. Integration with Ecosystem Architecture

5.1. Integration Strategy

5.1.1. Integration of the anonymisation and synthetisation components within existing systems

There are possible primary methods for integrating the VEIL.AI service with other systems. The chosen deployment strategy must ensure that VEIL.AI's intellectual property is protected by limiting exposure to VEIL.AI personnel only.

1. **Web Service Integration:** The VEIL.AI service is preferentially deployed as a web service in a trusted execution environment that ingests input data via API calls. In this mode, hospitals can send data to the web service, which processes it and returns or writes the anonymised or synthesised output to a cloud storage system or a designated file system. Cloud storage is preferred due to its scalability, ease of access, and inherent security features, but file system storage may also be supported if required.
2. **Command Line Tool Integration:** Alternatively, the VEIL.AI service may be deployed as a command line tool. In this case, the anonymisation or synthetisation process is triggered directly from the command line or indirectly through another service that automates the command line execution.

VEIL.AI will provide assistance and guidance to configure the service in either web-based or command line deployments.

5.2. Interoperability

5.2.1. Ensuring compatibility with other components of the ecosystem

VEIL.AI's service will undergo testing of the full anonymisation and synthetisation process, from data ingestion to output delivery. Key aspects include:

End-to-end Testing: Testing will ensure that the deployed VEIL.AI service can access input data, execute the anonymisation or synthetisation process, and return or write results to the designated storage system. This includes validating the secure transfer of data and proper encryption protocols at rest.

Automated Testing: For environments where the service is used continuously or programmatically (e.g., through APIs or as part of an automated data pipeline), automated tests will be employed to verify the service's ability to process data consistently as part of a processing pipeline without manual intervention.

5.3. Integration Validation

5.3.1. Integration validation plan

The integration validation plan focuses on confirming that the VEIL.AI service functions as expected within the deployed environment.

The validation plan will include the following steps:

1. **Secure Environment:** Ensure that proper access control mechanisms, such as IAM, network ACLs, and firewalls, are in place to prevent unauthorised access to the VEIL.AI service, input data, or output data
2. **Input Data Connectivity Tests:** Ensure that the service can read input data from the designated input locations.
3. **Output Data Connectivity Tests:** Ensure that the service can write output data to the designated storage locations.
4. **Test with Sample Data:** Execute anonymisation and synthetisation processes using test datasets to validate that the service performs as expected in terms of functionality, data anonymity and data utility.
5. **End-to-End Process Validation:** Verify the full workflow from data ingestion, anonymisation or synthetisation, to the delivery of results to the target storage.

5.3.2. Validation of data anonymisation and synthetisation results

To ensure the quality of the anonymised or synthesised data, the following validation methods will be applied:

Exploratory and Confirmatory Comparisons: The anonymised data will be compared with the original input data to ensure that sensitive information has been properly removed or altered, while maintaining the data's utility for analysis or research.

Inference Attack Testing: The anonymised data will be validated against common privacy threats, such as membership inference attacks (where an attacker tries to determine if a specific individual is in the dataset) and attribute inference attacks (where an attacker attempts to predict sensitive attributes based on anonymised data). These tests help ensure that the anonymisation process is effective and secure.

Data Quality and Utility Metrics: Various metrics, such as information loss, data correlation, and statistical distribution checks, will be used to confirm that the anonymised or synthesised data retains sufficient quality and utility for its intended use cases. This ensures that while the data is protected, it still provides value for downstream analytical processes.

6. Use cases and future considerations

6.1. Use Cases

The proposed anonymisation strategies for each clinical use case within the PHEMS project are designed to advance pediatric healthcare by enabling secure and compliant data sharing while supporting research and analysis. These strategies balance privacy requirements with the need for actionable insights, fostering innovation within the participating children's hospital ecosystem.

During the PHEMS project anonymization and synthetization is planned to be done in all use cases to compare results quality and privacy protection-wise between original and anonymized OMOP data. At the PHEMS technical architecture level, anonymization and synthetization is a configurable service, which can be part of supported use-cases in the ecosystem.

6.1.1. Use Case 1: Pediatric Cardiac Benchmarking

The objective of Use Case 1 is to establish a benchmarking standard across pediatric cardiac institutions in Europe. By enabling institutions to compare outcomes data, this use case aims to foster collaboration, identify best practices, and ultimately improve the quality of care provided to pediatric cardiac patients. The benchmarking initiative entails the analysis of patient pathways, surgical outcomes, and quality measures, fostering a culture of continuous improvement across participating hospitals. To guarantee compliance with ethical standards, collaboration with relevant organisations and regulatory agencies will be undertaken. The dissemination of findings through various channels will facilitate the promotion of best practices.

The anonymisation plan for Use Case 1 entails the obfuscation of direct identifiers, ensuring that no personally identifiable information (PII) is accessible during data analysis. The k-anonymity method will be employed for quasi-identifiers, which include attributes such as age and gender, to maintain the confidentiality of the data while facilitating meaningful analysis. To safeguard sensitive attributes that could potentially lead to re-identification if combined with other data, differential privacy techniques, such as the addition of noise using the exponential mechanism, will be employed. These privacy-preserving strategies permit the secure sharing of benchmarking data among institutions, facilitating effective analysis while maintaining patient confidentiality. It is important to validate the utility of anonymised data to ensure that it retains quality for effective benchmarking and improvement initiatives.

6.1.2. Use Cases 2 and 3

The objective of Use Case 2 is to develop early detection tools for sepsis in critically ill pediatric patients. Sepsis remains a leading cause of morbidity and mortality in children, and the capacity to predict and intervene at an early stage can markedly enhance patient

outcomes. This use case aims to utilise federated analytics and predictive models to improve the diagnosis and management of sepsis in pediatric intensive care units (PICUs) by leveraging anonymised data from multiple healthcare facilities.

Use Case 3 centers around optimising treatment for hemophilia patients through personalised factor prediction and dosing schedules. Hemophilia is a rare condition, making it challenging to collect sufficient data for model training while ensuring patient privacy. However, within the PHEMS project, the federated data-sharing approach mitigates the lack of data by enabling collaboration among multiple hospitals, thereby creating a larger, more diverse dataset that supports effective model training without compromising patient privacy. This use case aims to enhance the understanding and treatment of hemophilia, ultimately leading to better patient outcomes and quality of life.

The anonymisation process for Use Cases 2 and 3 employs differential privacy techniques and generalisation/suppression methods to mitigate the risk of re-identification while maintaining the essential characteristics required for model training. Furthermore, record-level sampling and shuffling are utilised to reduce the risk of re-identification further while preserving data utility for predictive model development. An essential element is the iterative refinement of anonymisation methods based on feedback that will be provided during a hackathon for use case 2. This ensures an optimised balance between privacy and utility.

6.2. Future enhancements

As part of the future direction of the PHEMS project, we plan to enhance the anonymisation and synthesisation framework by integrating more sophisticated privacy-enhancing technologies (PETs).

Future enhancements will also encompass adapting the anonymisation framework to accommodate emerging data types and more intricate federated learning scenarios. For example, as the PHEMS project expands to encompass novel clinical domains and data types, including imaging data, the anonymisation methods will be updated to address these emerging challenges (Task 3.6).

We plan to actively investigate if a trusted execution environment can be directly deployed as part of the PHEMS Kubernetes ecosystem e.g. using Azure Confidential Containers. In this case, a separate Kubernetes intermediate service may no longer be required.

Furthermore, we intend to organise periodic hackathons and workshops engaging clinicians, data scientists, and privacy experts. These events will serve two purposes: to solicit feedback on the anonymisation process and to assess the efficacy of privacy-enhancing techniques in actual settings. These activities will provide a platform for collaboration, leading to optimised anonymisation methods that better meet the needs of clinical researchers and healthcare providers.

The PHEMS project will continue beyond the conclusion of the project period, with both existing and new members committed to exploring additional use cases. This will extend the project's impact and ensure the scalability and replicability of the proposed privacy-

enhancing technologies across different clinical domains. This expansion will entail collaboration with new stakeholders to ascertain their specific data requirements and privacy concerns, and to modify the anonymisation framework following these needs. The objective is to assess the flexibility and scalability of the solution, with a view to its adoption by a diverse range of healthcare institutions.

These enhancements aim to balance data utility and patient privacy, enabling secure, data-driven pediatric healthcare solutions and more effective personalised treatments across Europe.